

Medieval Irish Land Law as an Alternative Justice System in Nineteenth- and Twentieth-Century Ireland, Denmark, and Norway

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Introduction

The project to translate the corpus of medieval Irish law in the nineteenth century meant that, for the first time, the contents of the various tracts were widely accessible to those without specialist knowledge of medieval Irish or access to the repositories where the manuscripts were held. The project, which ran from 1852 to 1901, attracted a lot of attention from within and outside Ireland, mainly as the law tracts were considered to be of great use to philologists, but also in anticipation of the insights into Irish society—both medieval and modern—the translations would bring. As the tracts were published under the title *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*, a popular picture emerged of a more egalitarian and just society, which resulted in frequent appeals to ‘Brehon law’, as early Irish law was popularly termed, to remedy injustice in contemporary society. Even as more tracts dealing explicitly with the regulation of status in society appeared, this image endured. This article will focus on the ways in which laws relating to land and land tenure were appealed to and examined in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries in Ireland, and how discussions of some of the land laws were printed in newspapers in Denmark and Norway in the 1880s. It will begin by outlining the project to translate the corpus of early Irish law and the role of the Commission appointed to superintend the translation and transcription of the Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland and will discuss the publications of the legal tracts. This will also include a brief discussion of other translations of medieval law being carried out at the same time to demonstrate how this was part of a larger trend in European antiquarian research, especially in the Nordic countries. The second half will focus on the modern circulation of the laws relating to land. It shall cover discussions around the potential influence of Land League ideals on the way certain terms were translated and how contemporaneous commentators interpreted them. The article will

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

conclude with the presentation of a discussion of early Irish land law in the pages of some Danish and Norwegian newspapers in the 1880s.

The Translation of the Law Texts

After the topographical project of the Ordnance Survey of Ireland came to a premature end in 1842, the antiquarians John O'Donovan and Eugene O'Curry were employed by James Henthorn Todd to catalogue the Irish manuscripts in the library of Trinity College Dublin.¹ This ultimately led O'Donovan and O'Curry to think about the corpus of medieval Irish law and a potential project in translating it. This idea was received well by Todd and his fellow Church of Ireland clergyman, Charles Graves. They submitted a request for funding to the Government in 1852, along with O'Curry's transcription and translation of the *Book of Acaill*,² and were subsequently awarded £5000 to set up and maintain a commission to oversee the project and £500 per annum afterwards.³ As is well known and documented, the work was beset with problems. This included the initial promotion of O'Donovan over O'Curry at the first meeting of the Commissioners, though this was rescinded at the second.⁴ There were also accusations of incompetency in English levelled at the two, which saw their replacement as editors in favour of the Queen's College Belfast Professor of Jurisprudence William Neilson Hancock

¹ For a biography of John O'Donovan, see *Dictionary of Irish Biography*, s.v. "John O'Donovan," accessed March 22, 2022, <https://www.dib.ie/biography/odonovan-o-donnabhain-john-sean-a6718>; For a biography of Eugene O'Curry, see *Dictionary of Irish Biography*, s.v. "Eugene O'Curry," accessed March 22, 2022 <https://www.dib.ie/biography/ocurry-curry-o-comhraie-eugene-coghan-a6664>; George Sigerson, ed., "Eugene O'Curry's Statement" by Eugene O'Curry in *Journal of the National Literary Society of Ireland* vol. 1, pt. iii (1902), 147-59 at 148-49.

² *Ibid.*

³ Minute book of the 'Commissioners appointed to superintend the publication of the Ancient Laws and Institutions of Ireland.' Dublin, Royal Irish Academy MS 24 O 39/CG/BL/1, 33, 17.

⁴ First meeting held on 7 December 1852; second on 10 December 1852. RIA 24 O 39/CG/BL/1, 8; 11-12.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

and his assistant Thomas Busted in 1860.⁵ With regard to the allegations of incompetency levelled at O'Donovan and O'Curry, Éamon De hÓir suggests that:

[B']fhéidir gur dheacair leo glacadh leis an Donnabhánach agus le hEoghan Ó Comhraí, clan fheirmeoirí beaga Caitliceacha gan léann ollscoile, mar scoláirí; ba mhaith ann iad, b'fhéidir leis na 'curious tracts' a bhí le fail i nGaeilge a mhíniú do na fíorscoláirí, ach ba shin an méid. Má bhí an garbhtiontú a bhí déanta roinnt aisteach anseo is ansiúd – agus bí cinnte go raibh – is é is dóichí gur mheas an Coimisiún nach é deacracht an bhuntéacs ba chuis leis ach easpa Bhéarla lucht an tiontaithe.

[P]erhaps they found it difficult to accept O'Donovan and O'Curry, the children of Catholic small farmers and lacking university education, as scholars; they might have been good enough to explain the 'curious tracts' in Irish to genuine scholars, but that was all. If the rough translation that had been done was rather strange in places—and no doubt it was—the Commission probably ascribed this not to the difficulty of interpreting the original text but to the translators' inadequate English.⁶

However, the main problem was the simple fact that the task was enormous and resulted in several years' work. O'Donovan died in 1861 and O'Curry in 1862, setting back the project further, though they were replaced by scholars such as William Maunsell Henessy. Their deaths meant that their original translations were revised by the

⁵ As Graves's draft reports and letters to the Treasury in 24 O 39/CG/BL/1 demonstrate, one of the frequent justifications for the amounts spent on O'Donovan and O'Curry's salaries is their workload. It is interesting to note that whenever Graves and Todd are called to account for spending by the Commissioners or Treasury, they always outline how many pages of transcription and translation O'Donovan and O'Curry have produced.

⁶ Éamon De hÓir, *Seán Ó Donnabháin agus Eoghan Ó Comhraí* (Dublin: An Clóchomhar Teo, 1962), 101. My gratitude to Nollaig Ó Muraile for help with the translation.

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

later editors, Hancock, Thaddeus O'Mahony, and Alexander George Richey, with aid from Irish scholars, such as the aforementioned Hennessey. The first volume, published by the State Paper Office, was brought out in 1865; volume two in 1869; volume three in 1873; volume four in 1879; and volume five, with a separate volume containing a glossary, in 1901.

The translation of the corpus of medieval Irish law in the mid-nineteenth century was by no means unique and was one series of many different medieval legal translations. Some of these included the *Norges Gamle Love* series edited by P. A. Munch and R. Keyser. Volumes one, two, and three of this series appeared in 1846, 1848, and 1849 respectively. H. S. Collin and C. J. Schlyter edited the series *Corpus iuris sueo-gotorum antiqui. Samling af Sweriges gamla lagar* (The Collection of Sweden's old laws), and volume one appeared in 1822. In 1853, the first volume of the collection of laws relating to medieval Iceland, *Lovsamling for Island*, was published by Jón Sigurðsson and Oddgeir Stephensen. Vilhjálmur Finsen's edition of one of the manuscript witnesses of the law book of the Icelandic Commonwealth, *Grágás*, was published in 1852. Of course, the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* followed in the series of the publication of translations of English and Welsh legal material. *Ancient Laws and Institutes of England* was produced by Benjamin Thorpe in 1840 and *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Wales* by Aneurin Owen in 1841. While, based on the name alone, the production of the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* certainly followed its English and Welsh predecessors, it is worth mentioning the other European translation projects occurring at the same time, as they were also influential in the publication of the Irish material. Irish antiquarians were certainly aware of research being carried out in other countries, for example, several Irish antiquarians were members of *Det Kongelige Nordiske Oldskriftelskab* (The Royal Society of Antiquaries of the North—a Danish antiquarian society based in Copenhagen) and corresponded with several of their Danish counterparts.⁷

⁷ For more, see Ciaran McDonough, “‘Ireland and Denmark Are Specially to Be Named’: The Connections Between Irish and Danish Antiquarians in the Nineteenth Century” in *Ireland and the North*, ed. Fionna Barber et al (Oxford: Peter Lang, 2019), 17-39.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

James Henthorn Todd and Charles Graves were certainly aware of the work being carried out on the Icelandic legal material, writing in the *Suggestions with a View to the Transcription and Publication of the MSS of the Brehon Laws, now in the Libraries of the British Museum, the University of Oxford, the Royal Irish Academy, and Trinity College Dublin* that “more recently, the Danish Government furnished the means of publishing the Icelandic laws,—documents remarkably similar in their nature to the ancient laws of Ireland.”⁸ As a small country within a larger empire, Iceland was in a similar political situation to Ireland, making the translation of the corpus of medieval law of particular relevance to the above-named countries. Like Ireland, Iceland also lost its parliament in 1800, coming under direct rule from Copenhagen, though it was restored as an advisory body in 1845.⁹ The status of the vernaculars in both countries was also commented upon in the early nineteenth century: the Danish linguist Rasmus Rask predicted in 1815 that Icelandic would be extinct within two hundred years,¹⁰ whereas in 1851, John O’Donovan gave Irish another few generations before its disappearance of it and the other “Celtic dialects of the British Isles.”¹¹ Like Ireland and Iceland, Norway had also been part of empires during the nineteenth century. In the early sixteenth century, Norway became part of the Danish realm, holding the status of a territory. This lasted until 1814 when Norway was ceded to Sweden after the Napoleonic Wars. While there is no mention of the Norwegian compilation of the corpus of its medieval law, it may possibly have influenced the decision to translate the Irish corpus and may also partly explain why there was an interest in early Irish law later on in the nineteenth century, as discussed below.

⁸ [Charles Graves], *Suggestions with a View to the Transcription and Publication of the MSS of the Brehon Laws, now in the Libraries of the British Museum, the University of Oxford, the Royal Irish Academy, and Trinity College Dublin* (London: Macintosh, 1851), 6.

⁹ Gunnar Karlsson, ‘Icelandic Nationalism and the Inspiration of History’, in *The Roots of Nationalism: Studies in Northern Europe*, ed. Rosalind Mitchison (Edinburgh: John Donald Publishers Ltd, 1980), 77-89, here 78.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ Letter John O’Donovan to John Windele, dated 6th February 1851, Dublin, Royal Irish Academy, MS 4/B/10/117 (ii).

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

Though the project began in 1852, plans for the Irish material began as far back as 1843, when the minutes of a meeting of the Irish Archaeological Society, prefaced to John O'Donovan's edition and translation of *The Tribes and Customs of Hy Many* stated that "the difficult and laborious work of editing our ancient Brehon Laws, Annals, &c" is soon to be underway and that in preparation, it needed to be ascertained what, if any, materials were stored in repositories in Britain and on the continent, as these would need to be consulted before any real work could get underway.¹² Charles Graves and James Henthorn Todd worked behind the scenes in collaboration with the Treasury and Lord Lieutenant of Ireland to secure funding for preliminary work, including O'Curry's sample of an edition and translation of a portion of the *Book of Aicill*, a manuscript witness of which was in the hands of Lord Ashburnham.¹³ As his letters to O'Donovan show, Graves always had him and O'Curry in mind for the project he described as "the most important that Irish scholars could be engaged in" even if at the first meeting of the Commissioners in 1852, they first decided to hold an open competition for translators, which was revised at the second meeting.¹⁴

The Idea of Early Irish Law

Funding for the project to translate the corpus of early Irish law was granted based on an appeal by Graves and Todd to the Government for funding. As has already been mentioned, they submitted a pamphlet called *Suggestions with a View to the Transcription and Translation of the MSS of the Brehon Laws*. As might be expected, the proposal focused mainly on the philological value of the legal material, yet when it came to a report submitted to

¹² John O'Donovan, trans., *The Tribes and Customs of Hy Many, Commonly Called O'Kelley's Country* (Dublin: For the Irish Archaeological Society, 1843) p. 7.

¹³ Letter Charles Graves to John O'Donovan, dated 9 May 1855, Dublin, Royal Irish Academy MS 24 O 39/JOD/124 (vi).

¹⁴ Letter Charles Graves to John O'Donovan, dated 4 August 1851, Dublin, Royal Irish Academy MS 24 O 39/JOD/124 (i); Minute book of the 'Commissioners appointed to superintend the publication of the Ancient Laws and Institutions of Ireland.' RIA 24 O 39/CG/BL/1, 9; 12. See n. 5 above for the dates of the meetings.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

the House of Commons on 17 May 1852, outlining the work carried out so far and requesting more funding for the project, the focus shifted slightly. The *Report of the Commissioners* mentioned instead the urgency of the project, as the scholars able to carry it out would not be around for much longer, and that some observations about contemporary Ireland would be provided by the translation of its ancient laws. It was mentioned above that the publication of the laws was greatly anticipated for the insights into Irish culture it would give. This is repeated in the *Report*, yet with a somewhat negative focus. It is worth repeating the comments of Todd and Graves here in full:

There are some circumstances which would render the publication of these ancient laws peculiarly interesting in the eyes of the politician. It is not improbable that the habits of thought and action prevailing amongst the native Irish are reflected in the laws which they framed for themselves before they were affected by foreign influences, and to which they continued to cling with obstinate tenacity, even for centuries after they had been compelled to submit to British rule. The Brehon Laws were actually appealed to so late as the reign of Charles I. We must not, therefore, be surprised to find some traces yet remaining of their effect upon society. We would also suggest that good results would be obtained by exhibiting the real state of this country at a remote period of its history. It would then be found that false or exaggerated notions have been entertained of the well-being of society and the advancement of civilisation in early times. Ireland never enjoyed a golden age. It would be more true to say, that she suffered for many ages under an iron feudalism, which administered essentially different laws to the rich and to the poor. Ignorance on this head has certainly created in some minds an unreasonable dissatisfaction with the present order of things, and a perverse disposition to thwart the efforts of those who are doing their utmost to ameliorate it. Nothing could be more efficacious in dispelling such morbid

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

national prejudices than a complete publication of the ancient Irish laws.¹⁵

This extract certainly demonstrates that there was something to be feared in translating the medieval laws and that the laws had to demonstrate clearly that any references to better conditions in early medieval Ireland were “false or exaggerated notions have been entertained of the well-being of society and the advancement of civilisation in early times.” The phrase “Ireland never enjoyed a golden age” certainly seems to have been inserted to allay fears of any nationalist insurrections, as were the last two sentences of the extract. One vital point that can be gleaned from this extract is that it is the idea of early Irish law which is powerful and attractive, often more so than the actuality of early Irish law. Since the late eighteenth-century early Irish law was discussed outside of scholarly circles, for example in articles by Tobias Smollett in *The Critical Review: Or, Annals of Literature* where he is able to mention certain tracts and legal concepts by name.¹⁶ This also featured outside of the Anglo-phone realm: in 1864 in a newspaper published in Vienna—the *Ost-Deutsche Post*—in an article called “Das weibliche Kriegsheer”, the concept of a Brehon is applied to a kingly adviser with the explanation that “Brehon Richter—Brehon ist ein irisches Wort und bedeutet einen nach ungeschriebenen Gesetzen, also nach dem herkommen urtheilenden wandernden Richter.”¹⁷ The announcement of the project to translate the corpus in 1852 was met with a fanfare of praise from people who had an idea of what early Irish law was and why it was important. The idea of early Irish law became an important cultural point—frequently connected with the idea of a golden age or as a remedy to a modern

¹⁵ The Report of the Commissioners appointed to Inquire and Report concerning the Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland (1852), 3.

¹⁶ See, for example, his anonymous review articles of ‘The History of England from the Accession of James I to the Elevation of the House of Hanover by Catherine Macaulay’, *The Critical Review: Or, the Annals of Literature* 23 (1767), pp. 81-88 and ‘The History of Ireland from the Invasion of Henry II by Thomas Leland’, *The Critical Review: Or, the Annals of Literature* 36 (1773), 1-14.

¹⁷ *Ost-Deutsche Post*, October 17, 1864, 1. “Brehon judge-Brehon is an Irish word and means one of the unwritten laws and also comes from the judging wandering judges.” My translation.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

grievance—which was frequently referred to. This can be seen in such headlines as this “Divorce ... Ancient Irish Style” from the *Evening Herald* in 1982.¹⁸ The first line of the article reads: “any takers, girls, to reinstate the Brehon laws?” Here the idea of early medieval Ireland, when early Irish law, or Brehon law as it is here referred to, is part of the golden age narrative, highlighting the difference between 1982 when divorce was illegal and early medieval Ireland when divorce was permitted under the law. The idea and the actuality of early Irish law can be used to address a wrong when official channels fail to satisfy an individual, providing a sense of alternative justice.

In the twentieth century, early Irish law was cited in two court proceedings on fishing rights in tidal waters in Ireland in the 1920s, 1930s, and 1940s.¹⁹ The first hearing was in 1924. The so-called River Erne trial concerned six salmon fishermen who had been arrested for poaching from Erne fisheries. They counteracted that it was their right to take salmon, as that stretch of river should not be privately owned. In their defence, they cited the Magna Carta, and then early Irish law. The scholars Eoin Mac Néill and Daniel Binchy came to the aid of the defence, firstly by proving that early Irish law was still being enacted in Donegal in the seventeenth century; secondly by demonstrating that English kings had no power in that county before 1184, therefore Irish law was the only one recognised then; and thirdly by citing the following passages from the law tracts, arguing against private ownership based on the rights of a people to “the salmon of the place.”²⁰ I will point out that this was not the only time when medieval laws were upheld in courts of law; in 1862 the laws attributed to the tenth-century king Hywel Dda were cited in a court case over foreshore access in Anglesey, Wales.²¹ Even as late as 2017, the thirteenth-century law code *Grágás* was cited in a legal case involving

¹⁸ *Evening Herald*, February 11, 1982, 8.

¹⁹ “Days of Brehon Law recalled in Foyle Case”, *Irish Independent*, 17 December 1947, 3.

²⁰ For a full account of the case see Thomas Mohr, “Salmon of Knowledge”, *Peritia* 16 (2002), 360-95; here 366-7.

²¹ Huw Pryce and Gwilym Owen, ‘Medieval Welsh law and the mid-Victorian foreshore’, *Journal of Legal History*, 35, no. 2 (2014), 172-99.

a Mixed Martial Arts fighter in Iceland.²² It could reasonably be concluded that the translations of medieval law texts reminded people that they once had been functioning law codes and they served as inspiration for a recourse to justice when it was denied by contemporary legal channels. For reasons of space, it is not possible to fully discuss the dual nature of the legal sphere in Ireland during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, but it is important to note that the long implementation of medieval law codes in Ireland resulted in the idea of alternative legal spaces, which were perhaps more accessible to Irish people than in other countries during the nineteenth century.

The Recirculation of Land Law

As was mentioned previously, the publication of the medieval law tracts in *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* made the texts far more accessible than they had been before. Naturally, this drew many commentators on the topic and, as the project was of such long duration, this attention lasted across the second half of the nineteenth century. Such was the interest that even a Finnish newspaper in 1852 covered some of the debate in the House of Lords on the costs of financing the project.²³ Naturally, early Irish land law was a component of this and volumes two and four of *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* cover tracts relating to the ownership and division of land. The project to translate the laws began in 1852, which was after the formation of the Tenant Right League and their demands, later echoed by the Land League, of the so-called three F's: Free sale, fixity of tenure, and fair rent. It can easily be understood why the publication of tracts relating to land would be of interest to politically minded commentators. Many of the arguments were centred around the way the word *túath* was translated and what was implied by it.²⁴ To many commentators, the land owned by the *túath* was common land, which was divided up and apportioned according to the need of

²² “13th century body of law used in case against MMA fighter”, *Iceland Monitor*, April 12, 2017, accessed February 3 2021, https://icelandmonitor.mbl.is/news/news/2017/04/12/13th_century_body_of_law_used_in_case_against_mma_f/.

²³ “Storbritannien”, *Finlands Allmänna Tidning*, August 28, 1852, 2.

²⁴ *Electronic Dictionary of the Irish Language (eDIL)*, s.v. *túath* (people, tribe, nation) accessed March 22, 2022, <http://www.dil.ie/42241>.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

the individual for the benefit of the group. In his letters to Karl Marx and in notes for a history of Ireland, Friedrich Engels saw the land as being in communal ownership up to as late as 1600; therefore did not see the importance of personal possession of land in Ireland.²⁵ In his unfinished “History of Ireland”, Engels refers to the deaths of O’Curry, O’Donovan, Todd, and Petrie as hindering the progress of the publication of the law tracts, meaning that he was aware of the project. He cited from the first two volumes, referring to them both as “the *Senchus Mor*” and discussed the text’s value in re-creating conditions in early Irish society.²⁶ These views were later echoed by Joseph Fisher in an article called “The History of Landholding in Ireland”, published in 1877. In this article he argued that *Cáin Sóerraithe* and *Cáin Aicillne* being translated with the word ‘tenure’, as they were in *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* was incorrect, stating that:

These arrangements did not in any way affect that which we understand by the word ‘tenure’, that is, a man's farm, but they related solely to cattle, which we consider a chattel. It has appeared necessary to devote some space to this subject, inasmuch as that usually acute writer Sir Henry Maine has accepted the word ‘tenure’ in its modern interpretation, and has built up a theory under which the Irish chief ‘developed’ into a feudal baron. I can find nothing in the Brehon laws to warrant this theory of social Darwinism, and believe further study will show that the *Cáin Saerrath* and the *Cáin Aigillne* relate solely to what we now

²⁵ Friedrich Engels *The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State* (Lawrence and Wishart, London, 1977), 194. See also Thomas Mohr, “Law in a Gaelic Utopia: Perceptions of Brehon Law in Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Century Ireland” in *Errinern und Vergessen/Remembering and Forgetting: Yearbook of Young Legal History* eds. Oliver Brupbacher et al (Munich: Martin Meidenbauer, 2007), 247-276.

²⁶ Friedrich Engels, “History of Ireland” in *Marx and Engels on the Irish Question*, ed. R. Dixon (Moscow: Progress Publishers, 1974), 263-302 at 285-86.

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

call chattels, and did not in any way affect what we now call the freehold, the possession of the land.²⁷

According to Fisher, “The land system is called Tanistry, from the Tanist, an officer elected to succeed the chieftain, whose main office was to divide the land of the tribe among the living members thereof; he was, in fact, a trustee and heir to the land of each of the sept or clan, and made such a division as suited the circumstances of the case.”²⁸ Seeing the matter in the same way as Engels, Fisher argued that:

The tanistry system seems to have been based upon the idea expressed in Sir John Davis's description, lineage; the land had been the possession of some remote ancestor and all his lineage were provided for out of it. The Caen finny and tanist appear to have held the same office, and its main function was the equitable division of the land among the lineage of the far-away original chieftain. It may sound trite to say that even now every man has only a life possession or life estate, for all love to think that they can exercise a sort of ownership over their lands after death has put them out of possession. This right had no place in the tanistry system, a man enjoyed the land allotted to him while he lived, but when he died the living dealt with it as they deemed best for their own interests. But this system went further. ‘Land was to them perpetual man,’ the staple of his existence, therefore every one of the lineage possessed his share for life. The lands of the chief did not descend to his children, they, with his office, went to the tanist, the lands of the tanist to his successor. All the other lands of the sept were divided among the members; there was no tenancy in the sense in which we use the word; there was no rent, no eviction, none of the powers claimed under the

²⁷ Joseph Fisher, ‘The History of Landholding in Ireland’, *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, vol. 5 (1877), 228-326+424 at 248-249.

²⁸Ibid, 233; See Electronic Dictionary of the Irish Language (eDIL), s.v. “tánaise,” accessed March 22, 2022, <http://www.dil.ie/40018>.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

feudal system by the tenants in fee. This system of tanistry was essentially republican in its character, the land vested in the people, not in the Crown; its division was arranged by the elected officer of the sept or lineage; all its members were joint owners of the common estate, which was strictly settled in tail to the whole of the lineage. No man could sell the inheritance of his children, and there were neither landlords nor tenants. The two administrative officers, the chief and the tanist, had their own official demesnes, which did not descend to their children, but went like church land, or clerical income, to him who succeeded to the office.²⁹

Fisher's claims can be seen as possibly being influenced by the increase in land-related tension, which would lead to the Land War in 1879. Certainly, his portrayal of access to land can be seen in light of the demands of the Tenant Right League and, as was explained above, his depiction of Ireland under the Brehon laws seems to be viewing it as a golden age. His views were refuted by Sir Henry Maine, who argued instead that private ownership of land was actually in place during the early medieval period. He wrote that:

The Brehon law-tracts prove, however, that it can only be received with considerable qualification and modification, and they show that private property, and especially private property in land, had long been known in Ireland at the epoch to which they belong, having come into existence either through the natural dis-integration of collective ownership or through the severance of particular estates from the general tribal domain.³⁰

The impact of contemporary affairs on the translation of the tracts is emphasised by the Irish nationalist Laurence Ginnell, who took umbrage with the translation of *ciss* in *Ancient Laws and Institutes of*

²⁹ *Ibid*, 240.

³⁰ Sir Henry Summer Maine, *Lectures on the Early History of Institutions* (New York: Henry Holt and Company, 1875), 98.

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

Ireland as rent, arguing instead that it should be tribute and that the translators were influenced by the political events of their day.³¹

Fergus Kelly attributes the belief that early medieval Ireland was more egalitarian than the nineteenth to a misleading translation made by the editors of the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland*. He writes that “the 1865-1901 edition of the *Ancient Laws and Institutes of Ireland* almost always translates *fine* as ‘tribe’ rather than ‘kin-group’”. This misled Engels and other modern political thinkers into thinking that land was held in common by all members of the *túath* in early Ireland.”³² For those who supported Land League ideals and who wanted to see greater tenant rights, it is understandable why early Irish law should prove to be such an attractive concept. One such commentator was the Liberal MP Sir Rowland Blennerhassett and it is to the recirculation of one of his works in Scandinavia that we now turn our attention.

Irish Land Law in Scandinavia

It has not yet been possible to trace Blennerhassett’s original text. In both the Danish and Norwegian newspapers, the text is simply called “Irland”. It is footnoted throughout with references to secondary material on early Irish law, like Maine’s *Lectures on the Early History of Institutions* and O’Curry’s *Manners and Customs of the Ancient Irish*, so it is unlikely to have originally been a speech and was most likely a pamphlet. The text was serialised over the course of a week in February 1882 in the newspaper *Fædrelandet*, which was originally liberal until Denmark’s defeat in the Schleswig-Holstein war of 1864, after which it turned conservative. The original source for *Fædrelandet* is given as V.P. with the subtitle “af Sir Roland Blennerhassett,”³³ which I have also been unable to trace. The extract, referred to as number II, published on February 10, 1882 contains a discussion of early Irish land law. While the current space limitations

³¹ Laurence Ginnell, *The Brehon Laws: A Legal Handbook*, third ed. (Dublin: P. J. O’Callaghan Ltd, 1894), 69; Electronic Dictionary of the Irish Language (eDIL), s.v. “cis” accessed March 22, 2022, <http://www.dil.ie/9231>.

³² Fergus Kelly, *A Guide to Early Irish Law* (Dublin: Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, 1988, revised 2016), 105.

³³ “Irland”, *Fædrelandet*, February 9, 1882, 1.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

of this article do not allow for close analysis of the laws themselves, it serves our present purpose to present this discussion of laws relating to land. Like Joseph Fisher and many of the commentators mentioned above, this text focused on the division of land among the túath, claiming that individual members had rights to portions of land. Though the translator attempted to convey what a túath was for the readers, it is clear that they were not certain, as in some instances there are examples of code-switching in phrases such as *Tuathafgrændsninger* (the boundaries of a túath).³⁴ The unknown tract was serialised over the course of a fortnight in the Norwegian newspaper *Christiania Intelligentssedler*, at that time owned by an orphanage in what is now called Oslo.³⁵

As a former part of the Danish realm, the text is in Danish rather than Norwegian, but the fact that it is reproduced in Norway as well suggests that it might have had some significance there. The first extracts of this text in both the Danish and Norwegian newspapers were not introduced in any way, so it is not possible to definitively state why this text was translated and reproduced, but we might make some suggestions as to the interest in the recirculation of medieval Irish land law in the late-nineteenth century. As was mentioned above, Norway was in two different empires during the nineteenth century, so there may have been an interest in the situation of similarly situated countries. In examining mentions of Ireland in both Norwegian and Danish newspapers in the ten years before this text was published there, there are many mentions of political events in Ireland, as there had been all across the nineteenth century in newspapers in many European countries.³⁶ It may be that this is another example of other nations being interested in Irish political affairs, yet without being able to correctly situate the original English text by Blennerhassett, it is hard to say this with certainty. It is most likely a reversal of a statement

³⁴ "Irland", *Fædrelandet*, February 10, 1882, 1.

³⁵ *Christiania Intelligentssedler*, February 21-March 4, 1882, p. 2.

³⁶ See, for example, Hugo Vallentin's series of letters in the Swedish newspaper *Aftonbladet* in 1893, titled 'Breve från Homerule-landet' (From Home Rule Land). See Andrew Newby, 'A Swedish View of Galway in 1893: Hugo Vallentin's "Letters from Home-Rule Land"', *Journal of the Galway Archaeological and Historical Society*, 70 (2018), 1-16 for English translations of these.

CIARAN MCDONOUGH

made in the *Wexford People* in 1880, which captured the interest that the inhabitants of countries in similar political situations had in each other. On the occasion of the restoration of the Icelandic Parliament in 1874, the anonymous author wrote that:

Ireland cannot fail to feel a profound interest in the efforts of countries similarly circumstanced as herself, when they struggle for that birthright freedom of downtrodden nations which has ever been that daydream of her people, since the “Iron Lords from Normandy with the Saxons in their train,” came to despoil her of her most prized gem. And equally profound must be the esteem which she entertains for the men who labour for that great and exalted end, particularly if they be men of genius as well of truth, capable of leading a nation through the wilderness of slavery.³⁷

It is just as likely that other countries looked to Ireland for inspiration in their struggles against imperialism as Ireland looked to them. In this case, “Iceland’s dearest son” was the nationalist politician and editor of the medieval Icelandic laws Jón Sigurðsson, who had used the laws to argue for greater political and financial autonomy for Iceland, resulting in the restoration of the Icelandic Parliament in 1874.³⁸ Possibly other scholars had similar intentions in translating their corpus of medieval law and were interested in what would happen with the Brehon Law Project.

Conclusion

This article has demonstrated that, while the publication of the translation of the corpus of medieval Irish law made it more accessible in the nineteenth century, sometimes it was the idea of what the law tracts contained rather than the actuality which was far more attractive and useful to people. Even though an interpretation of the laws had been provided in the translations made, sometimes modern commentators needed to interpret these interpretations to suit their

³⁷ “Iceland’s Dearest Son: Her Sword and Her Shield”, *Wexford People*, January 3, 1880, 7.

³⁸ Karlsson, “Icelandic Nationalism and the Inspiration of History”, 87.

MEDIEVAL IRISH LAND LAW

arguments. As has been argued in this article and elsewhere by Kelly, a mistranslation of a single word could change a whole society into the more egalitarian one that nineteenth-century commentators might have wished to see around them. In a time when land was at the centre of political debates, the access to previous laws relating to land provided commentators with an alternative legal space in which to find what was lacking for them.

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